

THEORY OF LONGITUDINAL ELECTRICAL RESISTIVITY OF
METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES AT CRYOGENIC TEMPERATURES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a theory that predicts the longitudinal electrical resistivity of unidirectional fiber reinforced metal matrix composite (MMC) materials at cryogenic temperature. The Boltzmann equation is used; its solutions are central to the development of microscopic models describing MMCs. Using this solution, a triple integral expression is obtained to describe the change in the electrical resistivity in the matrix metal due to electron scattering from the fiber surfaces. At cryogenic temperatures, the longitudinal electrical resistivity is shown to increase by orders of magnitude for a decrease in temperature of only a few degrees below about 10°K. This effect is due entirely to electron scattering from fiber surfaces. At temperatures above this value, the resistivity follows that of an alloy. Beyond the nitrogen boiling point, predicted MMC resistivity agrees with experimental data. However, the prediction of resistivity at liquid hydrogen temperatures cannot be verified due to the absence of experimental data. Limitations of the theory are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

No theoretical analyses that predict the electrical resistivity of continuous fiber reinforced metal matrix composites (MMC) at cryogenic and higher temperatures have been found. However, a number of experimental studies on the electrical conductivity of MMCs and in-situ composites have

been reported [1-6]. In these studies, experimental results are discussed and related to conduction models that are either modified forms of the rule of mixture or simple equations based on Dingle's [7] asymptotic solution of the Boltzmann equation for electrical conduction in thin wires or thin films when the reinforcing filaments are either much larger or much smaller than the bulk electron mean free path.

As the temperature of an MMC decreases from room temperature, the composite resistivity is expected to decrease steadily until it rises sharply at cryogenic temperature. The steady decrease is due to thermal effects in the matrix that can be modeled as $\rho(T) \sim T^n$, where $\rho(T)$ is the temperature-dependent resistivity, T is the absolute temperature, and n is an exponent between 1 and 2 [8]. The sharp increase in resistivity at cryogenic temperature has been referred to by Dingle [7] and others [9-11] as the size effect. In the analysis of MMC resistivity, the fiber resistivity is generally considered to be orders of magnitude greater than that of the matrix material, since these fibers consist of ceramic materials or boron (B) or graphite (Gr).

In this paper, a theory is developed to describe the electron scattering process from fiber surfaces using a classical theory based on the solution of Boltzmann's equation. In a sense, the theory discussed is the inverse problem solved by Dingle [7] for very thin wires. The resulting triple integral is integrated numerically, and the results are applied to continuous fiber reinforced MMC. The present theory is applicable only to conduction along the fiber direction in the absence of a magnetic field. The case of a magnetic field is presented in two papers submitted for future publication [12,13].

THEORY

The theory considers a single nonconducting fiber (B, Gr, or ceramic) in a metallic matrix with the fiber along the z direction. A small electric field \bar{E} is applied in the z direction. Let \bar{v} be the electron velocity at a point \bar{r} in the metal, where \bar{r} originates at the fiber axis. Then, the Boltzmann equation in cylindrical coordinates is

$$v_r \frac{\partial F^1}{\partial r} + \frac{v_\theta^2}{r} \frac{\partial F^1}{\partial v_r} - \frac{v_r v_\theta}{r} \frac{\partial F^1}{\partial v_\theta} + \frac{v_\theta}{r} \frac{\partial F^1}{\partial \theta} + \frac{F^1}{\tau} = \frac{eE}{m^*} \frac{\partial F^0}{\partial v_z} \quad (1)$$

where e is the absolute value of the electronic charge; m^* is its effective mass; τ is the relaxation time for scattering; v_r , v_θ , and v_z are the radial, angular, and axial electron velocities, respectively; E is the electric field, and

$$F^1(\bar{v}, \bar{r}) = F(\bar{v}, \bar{r}) - F^0(\bar{v}) \quad (2)$$

represents the deviation of the electron distribution function F from the equilibrium distribution F^0 . Equation 1 can be solved directly using general methods from the theory of quasilinear first-order partial differential equation [14]. The general solution is [15,16]

$$F^1 = \frac{eE\tau}{m^*} \frac{\partial F^0}{\partial v_z} \left\{ 1 - f(rv_\theta, v_r^2 + v_\theta^2, \theta + \varphi) \exp \left[-\frac{1}{\tau} \left(\frac{rv_r}{v_r^2 + v_\theta^2} \right) \right] \right\} \quad (3)$$

which is the same solution found by Dingle [7] using an indirect method.

The function f is determined from the boundary conditions of the problem. It is an arbitrary function that must be even in the variable rv_θ , since F^1 has to be an even function of v_θ from the symmetry of the problem and is determined by the fiber surface. When $v_r > 0$ (electron motion away from the fiber), f_+ is used; for $v_r < 0$ (electron motion toward the fiber), f_- is used. If p is the probability for an elastic scattering at the fiber surface, then the boundary at $r = a$ is [16]

$$F(v_r, v_\theta; r=a) = pF(-v_r, v_\theta; r=a) + g \quad (4)$$

where g is the distribution function for diffusively or inelastically scattered electrons. Using Equations 2 and 3 with Equation 4 and considering the fact that g must be independent of direction, but F^1 depends on direction, the solution to the Boltzmann equation becomes

$$F^1 = \frac{eE\tau}{m^*} \frac{\partial F^0}{\partial v_z} \left\{ 1 - (1 - p) \exp \left\{ - \left[r \cos \varphi - (a^2 - r^2 \sin^2 \varphi)^{1/2} \right] / (\tau \sin \theta) \right\} \right\} \quad (5)$$

where

$$\varphi = \sin^{-1} \left\{ \frac{v_\theta}{\sqrt{v_r^2 + v_\theta^2}} \right\}. \quad (6)$$

Scattering from the fiber surface occurs only when $v_r > 0$ and when $0 < \varphi < \varphi_{\max} = a/r$ [15,16].

COMPOSITE CONDUCTIVITY

Figure 1 shows the idealized cell used in the following calculations. The fibers are a distance D apart, and their radius is a . The mean free path Λ for scattering in the bulk metal is assumed to be $\Lambda \leq D/2$ so that there is no overlap between adjacent scattering regions. Also, A_b is the area of the bulk metal not affected by scattering from nearby fiber surfaces, and A_{sc} is the area of the scattering regions centered on the fibers within the cell. Then, the cell area is $A_{\text{cell}} = A_b + A_{sc} + \pi a^2$, which assumes that $A_{sc} = \pi(r_{sc}^2 - a^2)$ and $A_{\text{cell}} = (D + 2a)^2$, $r_{sc} = \Lambda + a$. Denoting j the current density in the bulk within the scattering region, then the total current within the cell is

$$I = \int_a^{r_{sc}} [j_0 - \Delta j(r)] 2\pi r dr + j_0 A_b \quad (7)$$

and the conductivity of the cell is $\sigma = I/EA_{\text{cell}}$, where E is the applied longitudinal electric field. If σ_0 is the bulk conductivity, then $j_0 = \sigma_0 E$. It then follows that [12]

$$\frac{\sigma_c}{\sigma_0} = \frac{A_{sc} + A_b}{A_{\text{cell}}} \left\{ 1 - \frac{1}{A_{sc} + A_b} \int_a^{r_{sc}} \frac{\Delta j(r)}{j_0} 2\pi r dr \right\} \quad (8)$$

and, using the values for A_{sc} and A_b , there results

$$\frac{\sigma_c}{\sigma_0} = (1 - v_f) \left\{ 1 - \frac{1}{(1 - v_f)A_{\text{cell}}} \int_a^{r_{sc}} \frac{\Delta j(r)}{j_0} 2\pi r dr \right\}. \quad (9)$$

The expression for the change in the current is [12]

$$\Delta j(r) = 2e \left(\frac{m^*}{h} \right) \int_0^\infty v^2 dv \int_0^\pi \sin \theta d\theta \int_{-\varphi_{\max}}^{\varphi_{\max}} \Delta F^1 v_z d\varphi \quad (10)$$

where $\varphi_{\max} = \sin^{-1}(a/r)$. The current density due to the background scattering is [15]

$$j_o = 2e \left(\frac{m^*}{h}\right)^3 \int_0^\infty v^2 dv \int_0^\pi \sin \theta d\theta \int_0^{2\pi} F^1 v_z d\varphi \quad (11)$$

where h is Planck's constant. Substituting Equations 10 and 11 into Equation 9 gives

$$\frac{\sigma_c}{\sigma_o} = (1 - v_f) \left\{ 1 - (1 - p) \frac{2\pi a^2}{(1 - v_f) A_{\text{cell}}} \int_1^{1+2/k} x dx \int_0^{\pi/2} \frac{3}{\pi} \cos^2 \theta \sin \theta d\theta \right. \\ \left. * \int_0^{\sin^{-1}(1/x)} \exp\{-k[x \cos \varphi - (1 - x^2 \sin^2 \varphi)^{1/2}]\} / (2 \sin \theta) d\varphi \right\} \quad (12)$$

where the following dimensionless variables have been used for convenience of numerical integration: $x = a/r$ and $k = 2a/\lambda$. Three nested Simpson's rule integrations were used in the numerical integration. The calculations were performed on a Hewlett-Packard HP-41C hand-held calculator. The details of these computations are given elsewhere [15]. Equation 12 can be written as

$$\frac{\sigma_c}{\sigma_o} = (1 - v_f) \left\{ 1 - (1 - p) \frac{2v_f}{1 - v_f} I(k) \right\} \quad (13)$$

where p is the probability for an elastic scattering at the fiber surface.

It is now necessary to relate k to temperature. No simple model has been found that relates the electron mean free path in a real metal to its temperature. Such calculations are extremely complex [17,18] and are not attempted here. But, a simple useful relation has been derived [15] that can be used to "calibrate" to composites. Figure 2 shows the value of the triple integral in Equation 12, represented by the function $I(k)$, as a function of k . A regression analysis shows that

$$I(k) = 0.27k^{-1.08} \quad (14)$$

with a coefficient of determination of $r^2 = 1.00$. Now, a linear relationship between k and T can be written as $T = Ck$, where C is a constant. To obtain C , the argument is as follows: at room temperature, λ is close to zero, making k large; this means that $\sigma_c/\sigma_o = (1 - v_f)$, as it should. One can take $k = 100$ for room temperature (Figure 2), which corresponds to small $I(k)$ ($\sim 2 \times 10^{-3}$) and, letting room temperature $T_R \approx 300^\circ \text{K}$, then

$$T = 3k . \quad (15)$$

Combining Equations 13 through 15 gives the composite conductivity in terms of temperature and fiber volume fraction as

$$\frac{\sigma_c}{\sigma_o} = (1 - v_f) \left\{ 1 - 1.77 \left(\frac{v_f}{1 - v_f} \right) T^{-1.08} \right\} . \quad (16)$$

In Equation 13, it has been assumed that $p \equiv 0$ because microstructural examination of fiber surfaces shows them to be highly irregular compared to lattice dimensions; hence, electrons are scattered diffusively ($p \equiv 0$) [15]. Equation 16 has a lower limit for $T = T_{\min} = 6\sqrt{v_f/\pi}/(1 - \sqrt{v_f/\pi})$, which was derived elsewhere [15]. This means that $T < T_{\min}$ has no physical meaning because that would give $\rho_c/\rho_o < 0$ ($\rho_o = 1/\sigma_o$), or negative resistivity.

DISCUSSION

Figure 3 shows the normalized composite resistivity ρ_c/ρ_o as a function of temperature calculated with Equation 16 for three values of the fiber volume fraction. This shows the steep increase in composite resistivity with increased fiber volume fraction and decreased temperature below about 10°K . This steep rise in resistivity is due entirely to the effects of electrons scattered from the fiber surfaces. At $T \gtrsim 10^{\circ}\text{K}$, the resistivity is essentially that at room temperature or $\rho_c/\rho_o \sim (1 - v_f)^{-1}$ as T increases, in agreement with experimental data [15].

The electrical conductivity of MMCs depends also on the postfabrication heat treatment, as discussed by Jenkins and Arajs [20]. They showed that matrix annealing temperatures ranging from 298 to 873°K will result in a general reduction in the composite resistivity of about a factor of 2. These data are for 28 v/o Gr/Al where the Gr fiber was Thornel 50. They also showed that the decrease in resistivity with increasing annealing temperature for 28 v/o Gr/Al is linear. However, this appears to be incorrect. Despite the large error bars in their data, the distribution in the datum points would indicate that this decrease follows the recovery and recrystallization profiles for heat treated alloys [21].

Aside from resistivity decreases due to annealing, Jenkins and Arajs [20] also observed a linear decrease in resistivity with temperature of about a factor of 2.5 for the same composite within a temperature range decreasing from 290 to 80°K . This linear decrease is due to thermal effects

in the alloy and has nothing to do with electron scattering effects discussed in this paper. This linear decrease was also observed for 60 v/o B/Al in the axial and transverse directions [19]. The linear decrease can be well represented by a functional relationship of the form $\rho_o(T)/\rho_o(T_R) = (295/T)^C$, where $\rho_o(T_R)$ is the bulk matrix resistivity at room temperature, T_R , taken as $3.3 \times 10^{-6} \Omega \text{ cm}$ [20], and the constant $C = -1.45$ for the same data [20]. This expression is not valid when $T/\theta \lesssim 0.2$, or about 78°K for Al, where θ is the Debye temperature [18].

The theory discussed in this paper presents some difficulties. It does not account for the overlapping electron scattering regions (Figure 1), the effects of which have not yet been calculated. In real composites, the arrays of fibers are arranged in a somewhat random fashion [22] for very small-diameter fibers. This gives rise to overlapping regions. As the size of reinforcing fiber increases, order appears out of randomness and the fiber distribution appears as quasi-square or hexagonal arrays [23]. This is due mostly to fabrication methods. For small-diameter closely-spaced fibers, many fibers are in physical contact. Consequently, the degree of overlap in the scattering regions varies a great deal. Within such overlapping regions, contributions to electron scattering can come from several fibers [15]. Consequently, the integral in Equation 12 must be modified.

It is known from the theory of metals that electron transport is very sensitive to lattice defects and impurities. In a pure crystal, electron motion is unimpeded except by thermal effects at high temperatures. Thus, one would expect the mean free path in a pure crystal at low temperature to be very large, on the order of 10^3 to $10^5 \mu\text{m}$ [24]. The value of the resistivity in pure metals is generally proportional to the absolute temperature for $T \sim \theta$, where θ is the Debye temperature. When $T \ll \theta$, the resistivity is $\rho \sim T^5/M\theta^6$, where M is the mass of the lattice atoms and for Al, $\theta = 390^\circ\text{K}$. On the other hand, the resistivity of a metal containing foreign atoms in solid solution is nearly always greater than that of the pure metal, and the increase is considerable in many cases. In general, this increase is independent of temperature (Matthiessen's rule) [18].

The greatest weakness of the theory presented in this paper is the connection made between the integral $I(k)$ and T through an assumed linearity between k and T . Thus, some arbitrariness exists in selecting the lowest temperature, in other words, in "calibrating" the theory by means of a

parameter in the absence of data. A physical approach is to relate Λ to T from a detailed theory supported by experimental data. As far as is known, this has not been done for MMC at liquid hydrogen or liquid helium temperatures [25]. The mean free path Λ is a function of lattice defects and impurities and alloy structure. Typical grain dimensions in Al alloys are on the order of 1 to 10 μm . Consequently, at cryogenic temperatures, one would expect the upper limit of the electron mean free path not to exceed 1 to 10 μm . Thus, taking $\Lambda \approx 5 \mu\text{m}$, $k \approx 2a/\Lambda = 10/5 = 2$ when the fiber diameter is approximately 10 μm and, from the relation $T = 3k$, it is found that $T \approx 6^\circ\text{K}$. According to the theory developed in this paper, at this temperature, $\rho_c/\rho_o \approx 1.17$ to 1.38 for $V_f = 0.25$ to 0.50, respectively. However, these estimates are based upon the constant $C = 3$, which was derived from heuristic arguments [15]. Therefore, T_q is not adequately defined. For obvious reasons, $T = 0$ cannot be used because then $\rho_c/\rho_o < 0$ in this model. Then, the conclusion is that, in the absence of an adequate theory for Λ as a function of T and the apparent lack of experimental data [25], the present theory can only predict the trend expected in the composite resistivity at cryogenic temperatures.

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Figure 1. Idealized composite cell used in deriving MMC conductivity model.

Figure 2. Values of the integral $I(k)$ as a function of k ($k = 2a/\Lambda$).

Figure 3. Normalized composite resistivity as a function of temperature at cryogenic temperatures.